

OVERVIEW OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN ITALY

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Abstract

In Italy, current tourism legislation unequivocally recognizes the right to vacation for all. The constitutional dictate has been implemented first and foremost by legislation on the removal of architectural barriers, which provides for conditions of accessibility in all public and private spaces. This legislation (although highly disregarded ed.) regulates design related to the construction of new buildings and renovation of existing buildings.

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In Italy, the legislation on tourism in force unequivocally recognizes the right to vacation for everyone. The constitutional provision was primarily implemented by the legislation on the removal of architectural barriers which provides for conditions of accessibility in all public and private spaces. This legislation (even if strongly disregarded editor's note) regulates the design relating to the construction of new buildings and the renovation of existing buildings.

Article 3 of the Constitution is also implemented in the specific legislation on tourism where article 1 of the new framework law on tourism recognizes the "strategic role of tourism for the cultural and social growth of the person and the community and to encourage relations between different peoples", implying the country's commitment to promote actions to overcome the obstacles that hinder the use of tourist services by citizens, with particular reference to young people, the elderly, people with reduced mobility and/or or sensory. Le più recenti tendenze, con l'emergere di nuovi turismi e con la frammentazione delle proposte turistiche, hanno posto la necessità di una politica globale del settore che comprenda sia il rispetto dei territori nelle loro componenti, quanto la piena soddisfazione dei turisti.

In Italy, an initial response can be found in the first Framework Law, and respective Implementing Decree, on Tourism which insert many activities into the tourism system which thus receive official recognition.

Decree No. 135 introduces substantial changes in the national tourism system, in fact many activities carried out without the exclusive form of enterprise receive official recognition.

The concept of < tourism >, of the activities aimed at:

the use of free time; to the well-being of the person; to cultural enrichment; the enhancement of traditions, cultural and naturalistic characteristics, products and the socio-economic potential of the territory; equestrian tourism; fishing tourism; of fish tourism; diving; youth tourism; Social Tourism.

The main destinations in Italy are:

- places of cultural interest (47.3%)
- seaside destinations (29.3%)
- the mountain (15.7%).

The price lever also leaves room for the more relational aspects of the holiday experience, sharing with friends and relatives and discovering the identity of the place and the people through contact with the habits and customs of the population.

The hospitality of friends and relatives and the possibility of staying in a private home for tourism purposes also represent a choice of economic opportunity.

The cultural offer is an integral part of the holiday even though it does not match the original image of the tourist destination, being not very incisive in the decision-making phase of the tourist.

Knowing the local identity manifests itself as an activity to be practiced during the holiday, positioning itself in the lead (30.9%), hand in hand with the tasting of local food and wine products (30.3%) both in Italy.

Holiday motivation

Communication channels that influenced the choice

The preferred channels for choosing the holiday destination are: personal experience 22.7%, word of mouth 20.8%, advertising 16.8% Web information 7.2%

The company

Tourists spend their holidays: with the family or in a group 60%; in the company of a partner 26.5%

Performed activities

Among the activities carried out during the course of the holiday in Italy, tourists mainly dedicate themselves to:

- visiting the natural beauty of the area (41.9%), monuments and sites of archaeological interest 24.1% , museums and temporary exhibitions 16.3% ;

- tastings of typical local products 43.4%, purchases of typical handicrafts 17.9 and shopping 22.42;

- the practice of sporting activities, especially as regards holidays in the second half of the year (35.4% against 14.3% of holidaymakers in the first semester);

- participation in folkloristic-cultural events 14.5% and theatrical, cinematographic 18.5% and musical performances 11.2%.

Type of accommodation

- Among the accommodation preferred by tourists, hotels are in first place (64%), especially in medium-range hotels (52.9% - 3 stars:);

- while B&Bs stand out among non-hotel structures (almost 12%).

Official accommodation in Italy.

In Italy, in 2020, there were 226,855 accommodation establishments (hotel and non-hotel) with more than 5.2 million beds.

Tourism is an important resource of the national economy and its development has a significant impact on the economic activity sectors of the manufacturing and service sectors. The statistics on tourism supply and demand outline a summary picture of Italy's attractive power and reception capacity, known for its extraordinary wealth in terms of coastal and mountain areas and cities of art.

In short

- In 2020, in Italy, there are 32,202 hotels and almost 195,000 non-hotel establishments offering, overall, around 5.2 million beds. The largest accommodation capacity is in the North-East, with 1.8 million beds.

- In 2020, nationwide the number of hotels decreased by -1.6%, while there was a substantial growth in the number of non-hotel establishments (+4.9%).

- On average, in Italy, in 2020, there are 86.4 beds for every thousand inhabitants, compared to a European average of 62.4.

- In 2020, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, an unprecedented drop in both arrivals (-57.6%) and overnight stays (-52.3%) was recorded for hospitality establishments, while it increased by 0.42 days the average stay (3.74 nights).

- Trentino-Alto Adige/Sudtirol, Veneto, Emilia-Romagna and Tuscany are the Regions that recorded the highest number of tourist presences in 2020 (about 52.8% of the total presences recorded in Italy).

- In 2020, the tourist demand of the resident population suffered the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, recording an unprecedented contraction: trips made on the national territory, for vacation and

work reasons, fell to 34 million and 130 thousand (-37.1% compared to 2019), for a total of 202 million and 673 thousand overnight stays in collective and private accommodation (-27.2% compared to 2019).

- In 2019, before the COVID-19 pandemic, in Italy 39.7% of residents aged 15 and over took at least one long holiday (of 4 nights or more). Therefore, Italy is below the European average (49.8%).

- The average length of stay in accommodation facilities is 3.74 nights, up on the previous year (+0.42 nights), with growing values both for residents in Italy (+0.39 nights) and for residents abroad (-0.57 nights).

In 2020, the tourist demand of the resident population suffered the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, recording an unprecedented contraction: trips made on the national territory, for vacation and work reasons, fell to 34 million and 130 thousand (- 37.1% compared to 2019), for a total of 202 million and 673 thousand overnight stays in collective and private accommodation (-27.2%). The most significant drop is seen in the segment of travel for business reasons, which is reduced to just over a third of those made in 2020, representing, in 2020, just 6.3% of trips and 3.3% of overnight stays spent travelling.

Catering in Italy

Catering in Italy is one of the sectors that brings the greatest employment, both for permanent and seasonal workers. An area that has recorded a significant decline, following the start of the pandemic today, and it is good news, finally recovering.

In this article we offer you an analysis on the state of health of catering in Italy, providing you with data, statistics and new trends. It is good to specify that they are constantly updated, which is why they must be taken with the right perspective.

In Italy there are about 220,000 companies active in the catering sector. An important number despite the setback recorded in recent years due to the Covid-19 emergency. This number does not include bars, but rather only restaurants and pizzerias.

The 20213 Catering Report provides an exhaustive picture of the situation, which tells of a stability that is still struggling to arrive. In fact, the pandemic lasted quite a long time, leaving 86% of companies below pre-pandemic levels. The impact of the Green Pass was also negative, especially in the summer of 2021, when over 17 million Italians have not yet been vaccinated, or about a third of potential customers.

Fortunately, today the prospects are different, thanks to the improvement of the health situation and the easing of restrictions by the government. Complicating a trend that could be even more positive is the uncertainty of the war in Ukraine, which leaves unclear shadows for the future of the entire national economy, including the restaurant sector in Italy.

The numbers for the two-year period 2020-2021

Again, according to the analysis provided by the report, there were more than 23,000 catering companies in Italy that recorded a cessation of activity in 2021, to which must be added those that closed their shutters in 2020, for a total of 45,000 closures of activities approx.

Data that confirms that tourism and catering represent the sectors most affected by the pandemic, with losses that in 2021 alone came close to 34 billion euros, equal to 56 billion if those touched in 2020 are added.

Catering in Italy today. Fortunately, the pandemic has left a legacy of some positive elements, changed habits and launched trends. Among these are food delivery and take away, which are growing strongly also due to the fact that there are several professions that have maintained smart working.

Furthermore, the attention dedicated to food safety and the sanitization of premises has grown, as well as to the image to be proposed on social networks, which have become an essential means of communication.

The best way to become competitive again, now that the conditions have significantly changed, seems to be that of investing, riding on the new gastronomic and production trends in the sector. Focusing on economic, identity, cultural, tourist values and digital technology.

In Italy today, according to data published by Fipe in January 2020, there are a total of – including restaurants and bars offering hot and cold dishes – 333,640 businesses in business. The employed in the sector are more than one million and 200 thousand (1,252,260), with 864,062 employees and 388,202 self-employed workers.

33% of businesses are run by a woman and 11% by a foreign citizen.

The restaurant industry is therefore confirmed as a strategic asset and a crucial sector of the Italian economy, with an annual turnover of 85.3 billion euros, and with growth that is certainly significant in some sectors (the take away sector - sandwich shops - kebab, for example, has grown by 54.7% over the past decade).

Food consumption outside the home now reaches around 36% of total food consumption in our country, the Italian catering market is the second largest in Europe (after the Spanish one), and food is growing in the domestic consumption of food and drink delivery: in the last year, 30.2% of Italians ordered a lunch or dinner online at least once, receiving them directly at home, and the sector is still in its infancy in Italy (it currently generates a turnover of around one billion euros euro) but is constantly growing.

However, there is a criticality in the restaurant sector in Italy, and it is a problem that concerns the high turnover among the new players on the market and the reduced average life of the new establishments:

- 25% of new restaurants that open in Italy close within a year of opening,
- 50% close within three years
- 57% "throw in the towel" after just five years.

Job

The theme of work is undoubtedly the great emergency triggered by covid and the restrictive measures introduced in the public establishments sector.

In terms of employees, companies in the sector lost over 243 thousand units in 2020, which were only minimally recovered during 2021. The result is that in this last year the number of employees is still 194 thousand units lower than the 2019 levels.⁴

The dispersion of skills is referred to by 28% of companies that declare that they have lost some of their collaborators and, in particular, 21.5% of these that have lost collaborators trained over time and with "experience".

Workers

Currently, 34% of companies declare that they have fewer employees than in 2019. If we consider that in the sector less than one company out of two has at least one employee, it is easy to imagine how the reduction in personnel concerns the vast majority of activities. With this warning and looking at the glass as half full, rather than half empty, it should be noted that 65% of companies have managed to maintain the employment levels of the pre-pandemic period despite such a difficult economic situation.

The need to recover the human capital lost in the year of the lockdown led 32.6% of the public businesses interviewed to seek staff during 2021. Two out of three companies encountered difficulties in identifying the necessary professional figures with negative consequences on 'business organization. The main reasons behind the difficulty in recruiting staff are inadequate skills (40.3%), the shortage of candidates (33.5%) and income support measures that discourage job search (32.4%) to be interpreted also in the light of considerations on the unattractiveness of work.

But the problems brought to the "plate" by the pandemic do not only concern the exit from the sector of a large number of employed people and the difficulty of satisfying the employment needs of companies. The covid, or rather the restrictive measures taken to combat it, have created numerous difficulties in the relationship between company and employees. This was stated by 33.9% of the companies interviewed who recorded absences due to illness (48%), closures due to clusters of infections (38%) and difficulties due to the refusal of employees to get vaccinated (13.7%). In the latter situation there have been absences due to lack of green passes (47.2%), 'no vax' utterances in front of customers (29.8%) and even voluntary resignations to avoid the vaccine. The countermeasures adopted by the companies resulted in suspension from work (33.4%), non-renewal of fixed-term contracts (27.2%) and in a continuous action of moral suasion in an attempt to convince the rioters to join the campaign vaccination (13%).

Revenues 2022

Expectations are generally positive. 57.5% of public establishments expect an increase in revenues compared to 2021 but there is no lack of negative assessments among those who, on the contrary, expect a drop in turnover (10.1%) or even have no objective, almost to prefigure the risk of closure (2.6%).

The growth prospects in 2022 are negatively affected above all by the increase in management costs (62.9%), followed by the persistence of the restrictions introduced by the Government to counter the pandemic (52.0%), by insufficient demand both from point of view of potential customers and spending power.

Within the supply chain, the return to pre-covid levels sees a significant majority oriented towards moving the finish line further. 60% of the objective will be achieved in the two-year period 2023-2024. However, there is a good 40% who believe that the goal can already be achieved this year.

Prices

It is precisely on inflation that the greatest concerns of companies gather. 76.2% expect a further increase in energy bill costs in the current year.

A slightly lower percentage (72.5%) also expects a further increase in food prices.

Faced with an increase in costs and a not encouraging assessment of the propensity to consume, less than one company out of two is planning measures to counter the increases. These measures mainly take the form of an increase in sales prices (33.6%) and the choice of more competitive suppliers (28%). For 56.3% of the companies there will be no intervention on the price lists or anything else.

Research activity carried out in the field with direct interviews with public operators and stakeholders, in collaboration with the Co-Rector Prof. Phd Iris Cekani and the IARC research group.

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